

JOB STRESS AMONG TRANSPORT EMPLOYEES IN CUDDALORE DISTRICT

Dr. S. Thirumaran* & D. Baranitharan**

* Assistant Professor of Commerce, DDE, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu.

** Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

Abstract:

The transport plays a vital role in the development of our country. Its main objective is to connect the urban and rural areas. Most of the students and office goers are using the buses. India's passenger transport for small and medium distances is bus oriented and many other transport industries the safety of travelers and other road users is of prime importance. The main objective of this paper is identified and analysis the factors influencing job stress among the transport employees.

Key Words: Job Stress & Transport Employees

Introduction:

Stress is known as the "Age of Anxiety" as it is inescapable part of today's fast life. With the change in life style and social factors, stress has become inevitable. Stress leads to physical, mental and behavioral changes. Stress can be both positive and negative. If it is created by undesirable outcomes it is called as "Distress" whereas if it is created by desirable and successful effects, it is called as "Eu-stress". Minimum level of stress is necessary for effective functioning and peak performance as it can trigger your passion for effectiveness and ignite aspirations.

Stress:

Stress is defined as a response to a demand that is placed upon you. Stress is a normal reaction when your brain recognizes a threat. When the threat is perceived, your body releases hormones that activate your "fight or flight" response. This fight or flight response is not limited to perceiving a threat, but in less severe cases, is triggered when we encounter unexpected events. Psychologist Richard S. Lazarus best described stress as "a condition or feeling that a person experiences when they perceive that the demands exceed the personal and social resources the individual is able to mobilize." For most people, stress is a negative experience.

Transport in Tamilnadu:

Tamil Nadu is a large state with a high level of urbanization. Transport linkages play an important role in the development of the state. Road transport industry is employment intensive as every one lakh rupees invested in road transport, generated employment to 9.26 and 16.95 persons for buses and trucks respectively. Road passenger transport has been growing at an average growth rate of 9.7 percent per annum. The road share was only 38 per cent in 1951, but this has increased to 80 per cent in 1986. Tamil Nadu is backed by an organized "Public Transport System" like State and private buses, taxis, and auto rickshaws which makes communication within the State easier and comfortable.

These days stress is widely spread and common phenomenon. It affects not only the individuals, the companies, organizations, their personal families and last but not the least the whole society. Importance of Stress in general and work-stress in specific can be judged from the fact that behavioral scientists, medical scientists, management experts have covered the research on stress and its impact on individual employees, which include behavioral, emotional, mental and physical impacts on human beings.

Statement of the Problem:

Keichel identified the job stress as one of the key problems in the workforce for the next century. Job stress problem pose risks to workers' well being as well as to organizational performance. Hence, the stress is the universal phenomena and property of modern human beings irrespective of their occupation. Because each and every job has its own nature and accordingly it is generating a kind of pressure (Stress) over the respective domain. According to the above truth, the transportation sectors especially the public transport and its employees facing plenty of problems and issues in their day to day life.

India's public Road transport system are among the most heavily utilized in the world and, mostly run by government owned Transport Corporation, are comes under the preview of State Governments. In Tamilnadu Public Road Transport has still remained the primary and preferred mode of transport for most of the population. Buses take up over 90 per cent of Road public Transport in India, and serve as a cheap and convenient mode of transport. Therefore, the employees' level of job stress is vital for the safety and security of mass passenger population.

Today's work environment demands more and more, therefore a certain level of stress is unavoidable and upto an acceptable level, stress can serve as a stimulus to enhance performance and productivity. However, when the level of stress is such that an individual is incapable of satisfactorily dealing with it, then the effect on performance may be negative. Therefore, assessment of level of stress is important.

Stress has become significant due to dynamic social factors and changing needs of life styles. Cooper and Sutherland's research evidence indicates that a wide variety of workplace conditions cause stress, strain or pressure. According to the WHO report job related stress in developing countries is often made worse by a broad spectrum of factors besides the work environment, external environment and individual factors. Therefore identification of factors influencing job stress is considered as important.

Job satisfaction is the favourableness or unfavourableness with which people view their jobs. The importance of job satisfaction lies in the fact that it is closely linked with performance and productivity of a person and is affected by a number of factors. Happy employees are productive employees. In fact, job satisfaction has been linked to individual outcomes as well as job related stress. McGowan confirmed the negative impact of stress on job satisfaction at the same vein the respondents' who succeeded to coping with stress were related to higher levels of job satisfaction. Furthermore, Blegen's meta-analysis confirmed that occupational stress is a major factor related to the job satisfaction. Hence, level of stress has significant impact on job satisfaction and job performance. In this vein, the impact of job stress on job satisfaction is considered.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To identify and analysis the factors influencing job stress among the transport employees in the study area.
- ✓ To analysis the impact of job stresses on the transport employees' satisfactions in the study area.
- ✓ To offer suitable suggestions based on the findings of the study.

Methodology:

Both primary and secondary data were used for the purpose of the study. Primary data were collected through interview schedule from the respondents. The secondary data were collected from various books, journals, newspapers, articles and some websites, etc.

Sampling Design:

Villupuram Transport Division is divided into six regions namely, Villupuram Region, Cuddalore Region, Vellore Region, Kancheepuram Region, Thiruvallur Region and Tiruvannamalai Region. Out of six regions the study covers only Cuddalore region. There are 11 depots functioning in Cuddalore region. All are consider in the present study. Among the employees working in transport sector drivers and conductors alone purposely selected for the present study. In Cuddalore region 1918 drivers and 1839 Conductors are working at present. Out of which 10 per cent is selected as sample under the simple random sampling techniques. The details is presented in following Table 1.1

Table 1.1: Sample Size

	Cuddalore I	Cuddalore II	Panruti	Chidambaram I	Chidambaram II	Vadalur	Kattumanarkoil	Virudachalam I	Virudachalam II	Neyveli Township	Tittagudi	Total
Conductors	254 [25]	244 [24]	164 [16]	212 [21]	183 [18]	144 [15]	67 [7]	185 [19]	175 [18]	83 [8]	128 [13]	1839 [184]
Drivers	251 [25]	243 [24]	165 [17]	221 [22]	203 [20]	150 [15]	74 [7]	192 [19]	188 [19]	96 [10]	135 [14]	1918 [192]
Total	505 [50]	487 [48]	329 [33]	433 [43]	386 [38]	294 [30]	141 [14]	377 [38]	363 [37]	179 [18]	263 [27]	3757 [376]

Source: Primary data [Figures in brackets denotes sample size]

Tools for Analysis:

The study used statistical tolls such as, simple percentage, Factors analysis, Chi-square test and ANOVA were used to analyze the data.

Table 1.2: Distribution of Socio-Economic Profile of Sample Respondents

S.No	Socio-Economic Variables	Respondents	Percentage	
1	Age Group	Up to-30	43	11.40
		31-40	166	44.10
		41-50	107	28.50
		51 and above	60	16.00
		Total	376	100
2	Educational Qualification	SSLC	62	16.50
		Higher secondary	170	45.20
		Technical/Degree	84	22.30
		Post Graduate	60	16.00
		Total	376	100
3	Designation	Conductor	184	48.90
		Driver	192	51.10
		Total	376	100
4	Marital Status	Married	250	66.50
		Unmarried	126	33.50
		Total	376	100
5	Monthly Salary	Up to Rs.20, 000	143	38.00
		Rs.20, 001 to Rs 30,000	120	31.90
		Rs. 30.001 to 40,000	60	16.00
		Above Rs. 40,001	53	14.10
		Total	376	100
6	No. of Dependents	0-1	90	23.90
		2-3	204	54.30

		3 and Above	82	21.80
		Total	376	100
7	Period of Service	Less than 5 years	56	14.90
		6 to 10 years	159	42.30
		11 to 15 years	84	22.30
		16 years and above	77	20.50

Source: Primary Data

1. Age Group: The age of transport employees is enquired to understand that which age group of employees constitutes the majority. Age of respondents plays a significant role in the cognition process. The age of respondents is grouped into four. It could be understand from the Table 1.2, out of 376 respondents majority of respondents numbering 166 (44.10%) are in the age group of 31-40 years, 107 (28.50%) respondents belongs the age group of 41-50 years, 60(16.00%) respondents belongs to 51 and above age group, and 43(11.40%) respondents are in the age group of upto 30 years. It is clear that majority of the respondents 166 (44.10%) are 31-40 years.

2. Educational Qualification: Educational qualification plays a vital role in job stress among the transport employees. The table shows that 170(45.20%) respondents are higher secondary level education, 84(22.30%) respondents are technical/degree education, 62(16.50%) respondents are up to SSLC education, and 60(16.00%) respondents are post graduate level of education. It is clear that most of the respondents' education is higher secondary level.

3. Designation: Table shows that out of 376 respondents 192(51.10 %) respondents are driver and 184 (48.90%) are conductor.

4. Marital Status: Needs and wants to transport employees may vary according to their marital status, because married may have to spend more than unmarried. Hence the study is made to understand the marital status of transport employees. It is shows that, Out of 376 respondents, majority 250 (66.50%) are married ones and remaining 126 (33.50%) are unmarried respondents. So, the majority 250(66.50%) are married respondents.

5. Monthly Salary: It is understood from Table that out of 376 respondents 140 (38.00%) respondents monthly salary is less than equal Rs.20, 000 and 120 (31.90%) respondents earning is between Rs.20, 001 to Rs.30, 000. Rs.30, 001 to Rs.40, 000 is the monthly earning for 60 (16.00%) respondents and 53 (14.10%) are earning above Rs.50, 001. Majority of respondents monthly salary is less than equal Rs.20, 000.

6. Number of Dependents: Out of 376 respondents, 204 (54.30%) respondents are 2-3 family members as dependents, 90(23.90%) respondents have either one dependent or no dependent, and 82 (21.80 %) respondents are having equal to and above four (4) members as their dependents. So, majority 204(54.30%) respondents are having 2-3 members in the family as their dependents.

7. Period of Service: It is clear that out of 376 respondents, majority 159(42.30%) respondents period of service is 6 to 10 years, 84(22.30%) respondents are 11 to 15 years services, 77(20.50%) respondents are the period of service is 16 and above years, and 56(14.90%) respondents period of service is less than 5 years. It is clear that most of the respondents period of service is 6 to 10 years.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Transport Corporation should organized regular eye and health checkups to the employees.
- ✓ Implement attractive system of reward and recognition of good work.

- ✓ Proper maintenance of buses should be required to retain the existing and attracting the new passengers.
- ✓ Transport Corporation should give training to drivers how to save the diesel, tire, and accident free driving.
- ✓ Proper training is given to the driver and conductors how to deal with the passengers.
- ✓ Develop an effective relationship with higher officer.
- ✓ Drivers are required to be well experienced and be aware of driving skills before embarking on any driving assignment.
- ✓ The driver has to produce an eye fitness certificate from an eye specialist nominated by the management before his confirmation in the service.
- ✓ To provide the children education facilities and recreation facilities in a better way.
- ✓ To provide equal pay for equal work and to increase the Pay-scale of the employees who work sincerely and productively.

Conclusion:

Stress in the workplace has become the black plague of the present era. Stress can make an individual productivity and constructive when it is identified and well managed. Some of the employees fear with the fact that low quality of their work puts stress on them. Stress has been identified to be a major problem in the operation of mode of travel. The transport employees key element in the system is very easily liable to stress in the course of carrying out his routine responsibility. Many factors that can initiate stress in the transport employees include road conditions, concentration on the road, lack of poor working conditions and design of the vehicle etc. Stress can be managed by identifying the sources, recognizing the reactions to the stress and changing the behavior. Taking stress management classes or rescheduling the work and personal lives can reduce stress. Having a supportive network of friends, family and professionals can also be useful in helping to reduce stress.

References:

1. Tarika Sethi, Ruchika Veramani and Monika Verma, "Stress Management: Its cause and effect", International journal of Research in Commerce and management, Volume 6, Issue 2, 2015.
2. Academic Skills Center, California Polytechnic State University San Luis Obispo, California.
3. K.Neela Pushpm and S. Palanichamy, "Road Transport in Tamilnadu", International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention, Volume 2, Issue 4, 2013.
4. Aamir Sarwar, "Work Stress and Family imbalance comparative study of Manufacturing and Service sector in Pakistan", Middle-East journal of Scientific Research, 2013.
5. Prof. Ugur Yozgat and Dr. Derra Yutkoru, Job stress and job performance among employees in Public sector Istanbul: examining the role of emotional intelligence, Published by Elsevier Ltd. 2013.
6. Prabhakaran, Veerakumar and Sumathi sri, "Industrial disputed in Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporaion, Tamil nadu", IJMMR, Volume 4, Issue 7, 2013.
7. Geetha V.Bathija "A study on Stress among government city bus driver in Hubli", International journal of Biomedical Research, 2014.

8. Hartesh Pannu and Prerna Tikku, "Outcomes of Stress: A study of Cause & Remedial actions for Reducing stress", International journal of Research in Commerce and management, Volume 5, Issue 9, 2014.